

Consideration on National Security Threat and its Financial Dimension

Grzegorz Waszkiewicz

About the Author(s)

★ Dr. Grzegorz Waszkiewicz may be reached at Email: ecogreg@onet.pl

ABSTRACT

Towards the large number of dangers to state security around the world we made an attempt to clarify the issue of instability approach within the political risk as well as to present its financial dimension. Presented paper consists of some parts. Firstly, we elucidate the place of national insecurity within the political risk. Secondly, short description of drivers from instability approach was made. Thirdly, we reviewed the results of empirical tests scrutinizing the insecurity threats to financial market stability. Next, interdependencies between national insecurity and selected financial indicants were depicted. Finally, we drew some conclusions. We concluded that internal and external violence poses a threat to national finance. However, financial market vulnerability to this peril depends on country economic and financial development.

Key words: political risk, international finance, violence, volatility

CITATION:

Waszkiewicz, G. (2016). "Consideration on National Security Threat and its Financial Dimension." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 2, No. 4: pp. 23–30. (Oct.– Dec. 2016); ISSN: 2415-0371.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Political risk and national insecurity

Political risk means a contingency that internal or external politics-related event that downgrades the position of given economy in terms of international economic, financial or political relations. Political risk combines drivers from political approach and instability approach (Loikas, 2003). The sum of different actors' activity from both approaches generates the level of that risk – Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Political Risk

Source: Own compilation on the basis of A. Loikas (2003).

Political approach pertains to unfavorable decisions and actions of state authorities (their behavior) on various levels. This approach is characterized by gradual transformation of institutional framework - changes in the rules of the game. This peril appears as a result of uncertainty between political and economic actors on the platform of formal and informal institutional drivers.

Instability approach concerns unanticipated events and changes that create national insecurity. That incident put politicians under high pressure and made their decisions ill-considered. Moreover, drivers from national insecurity area hurt domestic and foreign economic relations as well as national financial market. Finally, uncertainty grows in real economy as well as finance due to happenings from both approaches - Table 1.

Table 1. Political Risk drivers from two approaches

Political behavior	National insecurity
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Governance in particular project, firm or industry 2. Economic policy (Interest rate, exchange rate, inflation) 3. Institutional lacks 4. Social movements 5. Income inequality/poverty 6. Government actions 7. Supranational governance 8. International crisis 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Civil turmoil 2. Infernal armed conflict 3. International terrorism 4. Cyber Threat 5. War (external armed conflict)

There is considered economic as well as financial dimension of national insecurity. Economic dimension is linked to fact that secure country encourages own citizens to save, invest and production. Economy performs better when the number of dangers to state's stability is limited as well as when those perils are easy to predict (Smith, 2000). Therefore, economic dimension of instability approach pertains to the lack of variation in national economy conditions such as an employment, production and trade with countries abroad what supports economic development. Violence damages physical capital and diminishes production. Moreover, it hampers legal reforms (Jong-A-Ping, 2009) In terms of national insecurity in financial dimension we consider fluctuations of capital flows and bank credit as well as deviation in prices, yields and returns on financial instruments. Those volatilities may appear due to internal and external violence.

Consulting formidable value of global finance and its growing integration we ventured to claim that financial dimension of national insecurity is central to the modern international relations since it may provoke sudden capital flows in great scale.

1.2 Specific of national insecurity's drivers

Internal violence is connected with civil turmoil (political revolution, social movements, protests, strikes, civil commotions) and internal armed conflicts (insurrections, riots, mutiny, rebellion, military coup d'état, civil war) which may arise due to social mobilization or changes in public mood aimed at fight off corruption, creating political imbalance (or instability) and removing existing power structures (Hood et al., 2004). This kind of violence may be exported to neighboring countries so it has rather regional nature. Transmission pertains to emulative and imitative effects due to the propensity of social and political groups to emulate previous actions or behaviors from other countries as it happened in the Middle East during the Arab Spring (Emerging Risk., 2016). Relocating took place because of emulation, imitation, transfer of tactics and ideas. Moreover, common language as well as historical, cultural, ethnic, social, religious and political similarities between countries may facilitate this process (Emerging Risk., 2016).

Contemporary domestic conflicts have an economic or political ground (Brown, 2015). Most of them is linked to underdeveloped economies (such as Angola, Afghanistan, and Colombia) which are based on natural resources (e. g. diamonds, timber). Informal groups control those resources and they have a propensity to armed fights in order to maintain this situation. Contrary to the rich countries that are able to spend more on security (internal and external). For this reason, they decrease the probability of infernal violence, whereas the poor states have to tolerate infernal violence which is a major cause of underdevelopment. What is striking, domestic political violence may support international terrorism because terrorists may require skills (mostly military and organizational) that can be honed in countries that are politically unstable or have experienced political instability (Campos, 2009). Therefore, internal upheaval affects external violence to some extent.

External violence may be equated with terrorism as well as war since they are not connected with a specific nation-state or a geographical zone (cyber terrorism), that is why, politically motivated wars and terrorism do not create country specific risks but rather epitomizes international sphere of political risk (Hood et al., 2004). Nevertheless, international terrorism as a part of external violence is the most significant threat from national insecurity area in modern world since it triggers direct and indirect consequences as well as it poses the nagging threat to developed, developing and underdeveloped economies. Whereas direct consequences are harmful to real economy, indirect effects eviscerate financial stability. Moreover, terror generates uncertainty as to behavior of government and society. Attacks on World Trade Center (WTC) in 2001 raised the public consciousness of that threat because of its sheer magnitude, generating financial losses, vulnerability of modern society to terrorist attacks as well as financial commitment to national security that devours scare resources. Contemporary terrorism (new era terrorism) tries to obtain a political or social objectives through intimidation of a large audience, including non-military personnel and civilians (Rosendorff, Sandler, 2005; Czinkota et al., 2010) underlines three main interrelated trends such as globalization of commerce, travel and information; ascent of religious fundamentalism as well as access to weapon that dramatically modified the nature of terrorism recently.

The last factor is cyber threat. It shows a sub-group of political risk that may emanate from internal or external surroundings. That peril refers to attacks on computer systems and computer networks of financial and public (defense) institution (BIS, 2014). Cyber threat in finance means intentionally or unintentionally exploit one or more vulnerabilities within financial market infrastructure resulting in a loss of confidentiality, integrity or availability (BIS, 2014). The aim of those attacks is stealing money, data ransom and competitive information. In the area of insecurity, cyber threat is tantamount to cyber-terrorism that concentrates targeting strategic purpose (Cyber., 2014) in order to obtain confidential data from state institutions or paralyzing their activity in the Internet.

Recapitulating all above, war, cyber threat and terrorism epitomize international sphere of political risk therefore they are more susceptible to be transferred in global scale. Especially, volatility causes by terrorism is easily spread within developed countries with highly opened and integrated finance. The recent researches revealed that internal political violence, especially in less developed economies,¹ may be moved to other economies, not only through fluctuations finance, but also in form of unrest infection. This proved that not only uncertainty as a fruit of materialized national insecurity may be transferred but also original event may be emulated in the other countries within the same region.

2.0 RESULTS OF IMPERICAL TESTS

2.1 Terrorism (war) implications for financial stability

International financial market respond quickly to adverse events such as war and terrorism. Nonetheless, that scale of this reaction varies among countries and it is more limited on highly integrated markets (Nikkinen *et al.*, 2008). The terror attacks bring about both direct costs, nagging in short run (e.g. destruction of buildings or information system) as well as indirect effects which affect the economy in medium run through undercutting the consumers and investors' confidence in host economy (Bruck, Wickstrom, 2004). Moreover, terrorist attacks are dangerous to financial market (stock exchange) in country of occurrence, but also to other national finance (M. Hon *et al.*, 2004) stated that terror attack may bring supranational consequences against global connections among financial markets in different countries. What is notably important, the single terror attack has a special range of reaction on financial markets in various countries. The WTC attack in 2001 affects the whole world whereas the act of terror from Madrid in 2004 has rather local consequences (EBC, 2004). Additionally, adverse effects of WTC attack were finished firstly on American financial market (Chen, Siems, 2004). Comparing the attacks from Madrid and London (2005), it has been proved that untypical stocks returns persisted longer in case of Spain (Kollias *et al.*, 2010; M. Baker and J. Wurgler, 2006) stated that stock index was rallied in the aftermath of war in the Persian Gulf (1990) and the *World Trade Center* (WTC) attack in 2001.

When it comes to consequences of military action, longer term as well as wider range of operation should be noted. It is correlated directly with high military expenses (Caplan, 2002), what leads to budgetary funds relocation. J. Madura and R. Fox (2011) stated that possibility of war destabilizes business cycle. Probability of Iraq war, ten weeks before it really broke out, caused financial variables fluctuations (e.g. S&P index 500) that went up from 13% to 63% (Rigbon, Sack, 2005; Y. Shachmurove, 2003) corroborated that the war suppresses regional stock markets, what generates local and regional financial turbulences. (J. Simpson, 2007) testing impact of extreme political events (terrorism) claimed that it damages equilibrium and stability in economic and financial environment. What is more, the adverse effects are more robust and long – standing in countries with developed banking sector. Taking all financial segments into consideration, political instability hurts mostly less developed countries (Beaulieu *et al.*, 2005), probably, since there is more room for materializing its drivers such as internal, external violence and armed conflicts.

On the whole, the empirical analyses realized in the last two decades confirmed that political insecurity influences financial markets conditions. The peril from instability approach is usually linked to single adverse event that are hardly likely to be calculated by investors. Unexpected negative political incident cannot be contemporarily assigned to selected region of world however its results can be transferred internationally, what is broadly confirmed in the presented literature.

2.2 The scale of political instability towards finance – comparative analysis

¹ For balance, European mature and transitional democracies were affected by rising rate of violence because of sharing power between communities of people with widely distinct values and beliefs in process of democratization during the last decades of the 20th century (Karstedt, 2009).

Each national economy has incorporated certain level of national insecurity which cannot be changed in the short run. Nonetheless, the maintaining trends inform whether the insecurity grows or diminishes.

Table 2. National Insecurity in Selected World Economies; 2009-2016 (Global Peace index).

Country \ Year	2009	2011	2014	2016
Canada	1,31	1,35	1,31	1,39
USA	2,01	2,06	2,14	2,15
Argentina	1,85	1,85	1,79	1,96
Japan	1,27	1,29	1,32	1,40
Malaysia	1,56	1,47	1,66	1,65
China	1,92	2,05	2,21	2,29
India	2,42	2,57	2,57	2,57
South Africa	2,44	2,35	2,36	2,32
Norway	1,22	1,36	1,37	1,50
Germany	1,39	1,42	1,42	1,49
Hungary	1,58	1,50	1,48	1,53
Poland	1,60	1,54	1,53	1,56
UK	1,65	1,63	1,80	1,83
France	1,58	1,70	1,81	1,83
Turkey	2,39	2,41	2,40	2,71
Russia	2,75	2,97	3,04	3,08
Ukraine	2,01	1,99	2,55	3,29

In case of developing or less developed countries² the scale of insecurity is definitely higher than in advanced economies. Moreover, the growing trend of insecurity is observable in terms of France, Norway, UK and Japan. USA and Germany also experience that, however, to a lesser extent. That is probably the result of international terrorism since rich economies feel more threatened.

Financial dimension of analyzed dangers should be view in context of national government capability to encourage overseas capital to cover their public needs. Government has a special standing on financial market owing to the fact the state is perceived as a predictable debtor. Thus, public borrower should meet minor obstacles to gain foreign capital in comparison to other commercial companies from the same country. Above statements confirms to some extent figure 2 because rich and stable countries such as German and France relish the highest participation of non-residents in financing their debts, simultaneously, they feel quite secure in context of above-mentioned perils origin from national insecurity's area since some of them does not occur there. Experiences of some countries with poor national security (Russia, India) are in line with theoretical our expectations since they have little engagement of international capital in their sovereign debt.

² Besides Russia and Ukraine that are in state of armed conflict as well as South Africa (intense problem with infernal violence).

Figure 2. National Insecurity and foreign demand for sovereign debt; 2014.

Of course, conducted analysis is deprived of wider context, namely we avoid considering the specific and structure of national finance in each presented country. For example Russian public debt market is generally small whereas corporate debt (state-owned companies) is formidable. On the other hand, financial markets of many less developed and developing (e.g. some Asian states) countries are underdeveloped (weak financial infrastructure, institutional lacks, corruption etc.) therefore international funds are unwilling to flow there regardless of higher returns – Lucas paradox (Lucas, 1990).

On the other hand, previous, current and future stance of national security is discounted continuously by financial markets participants therefore national stock markets, in the first instance, are subjected to prices fluctuations. Large probability of unexpected and harmful events affect investors expectations what triggers the variability in finance on national stock exchanges. In the majority of presented cases volatility seems to be correlated with stock price – figure 3.

Figure 3. National Insecurity and Stock Price Volatility; 2015.

Source: Own calculations on the basis of Global..., 2014; FRED Economic Data. We employed GPI (data from 2014) and Volatility of Stock Price (data from 2015) in order to show how investors react to known facts

Low national security is linked to high price variability in Russia, Saudi Arabia and Colombia. Regardless of sound national security, volatility is high in case of Japan, German, Canada, UK and France. There are at least two reasons to explain that. Firstly, those economies have a huge capitalization of stock exchanges and capital movements are significance. Secondly, national security is relatively high-level and this factor plays a scant role in terms of assets prices variation. Contrary to that, Malaysia presents low volatility along with secured environment; however, low variability results from small capitalization (minor flows) in comparison to other Asian countries e. g. Japan. According to Lipinsky *et al.* (2014). Tokyo SE Group was 7 times bigger than Bursa Malaysia in 2012.

To sum up, whereas the growing national insecurity seems to impact negatively foreign demand for public bonds, it does not clearly influence the instability of stock prices. To some extent, countries with lower stock exchange capitalization may be susceptible to threats from this area.

3.0 CONCLUSION

Many economies are imbued with uncertainty resulting from great amount of threats to national security. It is generally known that the lower development of national economy, the highest level of insecurity (violence). Nonetheless, advanced economies are not free from security treats because of terrorism and cyber-attacks. What is more, rich countries have been experiencing growing security threat since 2009. National insecurity affects the level of political risk which is responsible for the credibility of given economy and its position in international relations. Therefore, taking country financial position into account authorities should be careful with underestimating instability approach in terms of fluctuations in global and national finance. Not only terrorism and cyber threat may threaten to stability in finance, but also domestic violence (civil turmoil) with its inclination to be spread among similar and less developed countries. Both results of foregoing empirical tests as well as casual descriptive analysis of country insecurity towards foreign investor demand or variability of stock price seem to confirm the interdependency between the lack of national security and financial indicants. The existence and power of above-depicted correlations rest on the economic, financial and political position of selected national economy in the modern world.

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